

Sustainable optimisation approaches for production planning and control to evolve towards industry 5.0

Blanca Guerrero^a, Josefa Mula^{a*} and Raul Poler^a

^aResearch Centre on Production Management and Engineering (CIGIP), Universitat Politècnica de València, Alcoy, Alicante, Spain

*Corresponding author: fmula@cigip.upv.es. C/ Alarcón, 1, 03801, Alcoy, Alicante, Spain.

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Abstract

Industry 4.0 (I4.0) has led to a very high development potential in the optimisation of production planning and control problems in industrial companies. This study aims to analyse the existing scientific literature on the optimisation of planning, control and management problems, specifically in the production, operations and scheduling areas, to make industry more sustainable in accordance with the I4.0 context; that is, applying new digital technologies and I5.0 by integrating people into this digital transformation. Specifically, 77 research works were identified and analysed. The main findings conclude that the key setting of these optimisation problems lies in manufacturing contexts and highlight the use of modelling and solution techniques through mathematical programming and metaheuristics. These studies, which are mostly empirical, point out different software tools, and underline the use of MATLAB, optimisation with CPLEX, the Python programming language and simulation through AnyLogic. For I4.0 techniques, data analytics and big data, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, sensors and simulation and digital twins are the most studied. Proposals addressing worker ergonomics and a three-pillar approach to sustainability are particularly noteworthy. Finally, the main research gaps, challenges and trends for future research are recognised.

Keywords: production planning and control, optimisation, sustainability, industry 5.0.

1. Introduction

In order to play a pioneering role in industries, in 2011 the German government introduced the Industry 4.0 (I4.0) concept, which describes how digitisation, automation and new technologies can revolutionise the organisation of global value chains (Nosalska et al. 2019). According to Kagermann, Wahlster and Helbig (2013), smart factories would enable meeting individual customer needs and the cost-effective manufacturing of customised items. With dynamic business processes and industrial engineering, flexibility to adapt to changes in production and to cope with supply chain disruptions would be achievable even in the limited and uncertain nature of supply in a postdisaster environment (Kamyabniya et al. 2024). In addition, intelligent support systems would develop routine tasks and allow workers to focus on higher value-added activities. Therefore, I4.0 is a set of technologies, organisational concepts and management principles that can improve manufacturing supply chains' performance, driven by

production cost optimisation, mass customisation requirements, connectivity and digitisation of factories (Mula and Bogataj 2021). Thus I4.0 seeks to combine technologies, such as cyber-physical systems (CPS), the Internet of Things (IoT) and cloud computing, industrial integration, enterprise architecture, service-oriented architecture (SOA), business process management, industrial information integration, among others (Xu, Xu, and Li 2018). For this purpose, models based on digital technologies and devices that communicate autonomously along the value chain are used to further enable real-time collection and to analyse production data (Li and Huang 2021; Xu, Xu, and Li 2018). This requires compliance with stringent conditions in terms of regulations, processes and labour organisation, product availability, innovative business models, safety and intellectual property protection, labour availability, research, training and professional development, as well as an appropriate legal framework (European Parliament 2016).

In this context, production planning and control (PPC) seek efficiency in meeting a company's production requirements by helping its managers to understand, control and make decisions. PPC system design is influenced by several factors, such as the volume and variety of planned production, which are often related to customers' influence on the design of a product or service. Therefore, PPC involve tools to define what, how much and when to produce, purchase and deliver efficiently to meet customer needs. The answers to these questions become the basis for work schedules assigned to humans and machines and orders to suppliers (Bonney 2000; Cañas et al. 2022).

With the integration of the human factor into I4.0 planning comes the Industry 5.0 (I5.0) concept (Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler 2021b), which seeks to improve coordination between people and machines (Zhang et al. 2021) in production processes (Groten and Gallego-García 2021). Thus I5.0 focuses on people-machine collaboration and uses emerging technologies to improve industrial production in a sustainable and people-centred way (Battini et al. 2022; Rega et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2021). It is about addressing the distinctive features of I4.0 (European Commission 2021), focusing on the worker and sustainability, and also posing new challenges (Bakon et al. 2022; Battini et al. 2022). The I5.0 initiative highlights the importance of human involvement in environments where physically demanding and risky tasks are transferred to systems, as well as the responsibility for decision making (Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler 2021b). In this context, decision makers are essential because they evaluate the results of multi-objective optimisations and decide which solution best fits the company's

objectives (Santos et al. 2022). Society 5.0 is established on the basis of human-centred information and communication technologies (ICT) and follows the development of I5.0 (Groten and Gallego-García 2021). Machine-human collaboration enables personnel to use their cognitive and thinking skills to provide personalised value-added services (Zhang et al. 2021). Digitisation and the use of new technologies link manufacturers, end users, end-of-life collectors and remanufacturers to achieve remanufacturing success in the I5.0 era (Yu 2022). In this way, I5.0 prioritises sustainability in the use of emerging technologies and places humans and the environment at the centre of the industrial and societal transition (Yu 2022; Zhang et al. 2021). Sustainable manufacturing is made possible by the convergence of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and by increasing individualised product demands. Ultimately, I5.0 is envisioned as sustainable, resilient and people-centred manufacturing (Leng et al. 2022).

Initially, the sustainability term was closely linked with the dimensions of production and economic benefits (Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic 2021; Trstenjak et al. 2022). However, it also intends to achieve economic growth and to satisfy consumer demand (Tsai and Lu 2018). Thus for increasingly complex production systems, operational decision making faces more challenges in terms of having sustainable manufacturing meet rapidly changing customer and market demands (Zhang et al. 2022). This perspective, if constrained, creates multiple problems for other dimensions and may neglect sustainability aspects (Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic 2021). Hence sustainable manufacturing is about developing a product with the minimum negative impact on the environment and with minimum natural resources use (Pawar and Bhosale 2022) to ensure sustainable human survival and environmental and economic development (Tsai and Lu 2018). I4.0 growth requires more sustainable production plans to continue to manufacture high-quality products (Tsai and Lu 2018). Digitisation in manufacturing has a mixed impact on environmental sustainability that is positive by improving resource and information efficiency, but also has negative environmental consequences due to increased resources and energy use, and to waste and emissions (Akkad, Haidar, and Bányai 2022). This will result in the three pillars of sustainability: (1) economic sustainability, by using fewer resources, time and energy, which increases efficiency; (2) social sustainability, by emphasising the rights or health of employees, the community and other stakeholders; (3) environmental sustainability, by using less energy, generating less waste and emissions and recycling resources (Akkad, Haidar, and Bányai 2022; Tsai and Lu 2018). To ensure sustainability and to meet emerging market

requirements, approaches like lean manufacturing (LM), greening and resilience have also been implemented (Aydin and Tirkolae 2022; Farooq et al. 2021).

Previous literature reviews by Suzanne, Absi, and Borodin (2020) overview research into circular economy in production planning. They do so by defining key concepts, suggesting the integration of recovery options into traditional systems for sustainability through discrete-time optimisation models for tactical production planning and focusing on recovery operations, greenhouse gas emission reductions and energy conservation in four categories: disassembly for recycling, product and raw material recycling, by-products and co-production, and emissions and energy use. On the impact of digital transformation via I4.0 on sustainable value chains and manufacturing, Felsberger and Reiner (2020) identify key issues and focus group discussions, and address gaps concerning the economic, environmental and social impacts of adopting new technologies. Hence it is worth noting the literature review by (Aydin and Tirkolae 2022) on sustainable and circular aggregate production planning (APP), which focuses on I4.0 enabling technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), the IoT, big data and smart manufacturing. It also discusses the importance of social sustainability in APP and the need to take into account economic, environmental and social factors, but without focusing on employees, operators or people. YounesSinaki et al. (2022) review the literature on cellular manufacturing design and I4.0 applications. Topics related to manufacturing design and technological advances are covered, including mathematical models, empirical research, simulation-based research and sustainability issues. The authors also highlight the importance of social criteria, such as labour utilisation, ergonomic factors, training, firing and hiring, for the design of sustainable manufacturing systems. Zhou et al. (2022) explore production and operations management for smart manufacturing by analysing the challenges that the manufacturing sector faces in an increasingly competitive globalised market, and how automation technology, robotics and next-generation information and communication technologies (ICTs) are being used to improve the adaptability, autonomy, flexibility and intelligence of manufacturing systems. It is noted that although attention is paid to the economic value of smart manufacturing implementation, the socio-environmental should be further investigated to achieve sustainable operations. Estes et al. (2022) provide an overview of the use and application of reinforcement learning (RL) techniques in PPC by focusing on five main areas: facility resource planning, capacity planning, purchasing and supply management, production scheduling and inventory management. Sustainability concepts are briefly

mentioned. Similarly, while noting that RL can potentially benefit employees and operators by supporting decision making processes and optimising inventory management, the focus does not lie in human factors. Finally, Bakon et al. (2022) provide an analysis of uncertainties in complex production and supply chains in I4.0 and I5.0 contexts by focusing on scheduling problems and taking into account future research in algorithm programming towards I5.0 in terms of sustainability and the importance of managing human-machine interactions for social, psychological and humanitarian reasons.

Building on these foundational insights, we address the analysis of PPC optimisation problems by contemplating the three pillars of sustainability but by also aligning with I5.0 principles, which emphasises human-centric innovation and sustainable development in the manufacturing sector. The main novelty of this paper is to address the analysis of the combination of PPC optimisation problem concepts and I4.0 and I5.0 techniques to achieve an industry that focuses more on the three pillars of sustainability and people. Here I4.0 promotes the integration of advanced technologies, such as automation, data analysis, AI and the IoT, to improve the efficiency and quality of production processes, and I5.0 can additionally generate workers' more significant commitment and job satisfaction and sustainability. To this end, the existing scientific literature is used to analyse how PPC problems can be optimised by including sustainability aspects in an I4.0 context that evolves towards I5.0. To define this and the following research questions, the CIMO logic is considered, which implies a problematic context for which the design proposal suggests a specific type of intervention to produce the expected results through (generative) mechanisms (Denyer and Tranfield 2009). Therefore, the focal research question (RQ) of this research is defined, which seeks to identify PPC optimisation problems to move towards more sustainable I4.0 and I5.0. The remaining part of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents the literature review methodology. Section 3 summarises the main findings using thematic, content and taxonomic analyses. Section 4 discusses the main findings and research gaps found in the literature. Finally, Section 5 concludes the article and points out possible future research areas.

2. Review methodology

In this systematic literature review, a methodology of search, selection, evaluation,

analysis and synthesis is applied to obtain an accurate overview of the current state of knowledge about the problem under study to identify existing research gaps. A rigorous protocol is followed. It is based on the previously specified RQ (Denyer and Tranfield 2009). It examines the current state of the literature about the optimisation of planning, control and management problems in production, operations and planning areas that are carried out in I4.0 or I5.0 to evolve towards more sustainable industry and manufacturing. In addition, further RQs are determined and different sources and studies from these are evaluated (Dekkers, Carey, and Langhorne 2022). So the proposed CIMO design of such RQs is as follows (Table 1): in the I4.0 and I5.0 context, along with their technologies, we wish to optimise (M) planning, control and management problems, specifically in production, operations and scheduling areas (I), to make industry and manufacturing more sustainable, green, circular or reverse (O).

Table 1. Conceptual blocks of the CIMO logic for the RQ design proposal.

Component	Keywords
Context (C)	industry 4.0 OR industry 5.0
Interventions (I)	planning OR control OR management production OR operations OR scheduling
Mechanism (M)	optimisation
Outcome (O)	industry OR manufacturing sustainable OR green OR circular OR reverse

The specific RQs are defined as follows: RQ1) What are the main characteristics of optimisation models and algorithms for production or operations management, and their solutions, that aim to move towards more sustainable I4.0/I5.0?; RQ2) What are the main research gaps, challenges and trends for further research in the optimisation of production or operations management problems to move towards more sustainable I4.0/I5.0?

Error! Reference source not found. summarises the employed review methodology, based on a step-by-step approach from Thomé, Scavarda, and Scavarda (2016) for research in the operations management field: (i) problem statement and formulation; (ii) literature search; (iii) data collection from the literature; (iv) quality assessment; (v) analysis and synthesis; (vi) interpretation; (vii) presentation of the results.

Figure 1 Caption. Flow chart of the review methodology.

Figure 1 Alt Text. A review methodology flow chart summarising the conceptual research stages.

This systematic review was carried out according to the following decisions, which had to be adapted to each particular search database: (i) conceptual groupings for the bibliographic search; (ii) document fields to be searched for each block; (iii) used databases; (iv) consultation dates and time periods to be explored; (v) documentary typologies; (vi) thematic areas.

Conceptual groupings were made up of the keywords that were selected after making various tentative searches with different schemes and a brief analysis of the results that they yielded. During this process, when including sustainability concepts as search criteria in the abstract, title or keywords of the document, the results were scarce and of poor quality. Therefore, a decision was made to approach this conceptual grouping by searching for such concepts throughout the document to, thus, ensure a broader and more comprehensive coverage of the relevant literature.

Search queries composed keywords which differed depending on the used database and its search procedure. The main employed scientific databases were Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) (Bartol et al. 2014). ScienceDirect, ProQuest and IEEE Xplore were also consulted. By searching in consecutive stages, the first search was carried out in Scopus and then in WoS. Then duplicate references were eliminated considering Scopus the main database. The same procedure was continued with the remaining databases by contemplating the hierarchy of the aforementioned databases. So the first filtering of the results yielded 383 papers, and the percentages of belonging to each database were as follows: Scopus (42.8%), WoS (15.4%), ScienceDirect (23%), ProQuest (17.8%) and, finally, IEEE Xplore with 1%. The Scopus, WoS and ProQuest databases offered more flexible search options due to two key features: they did not restrict the number of keywords that can be used in a search field; they allowed the use of wildcards to extend and complement character strings in the search (Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler 2021a). With ScienceDirect and IEEE Xplore, the words that employed wildcards in the other searches were considered by specifically adding variations of these words. It should also be noted that Science Direct did not allow more than eight Boolean connectors per field. In this case, the complete search would have more than eight connectors in the title, abstract or author-specified keywords field. Because of this, the keywords for the search in Science Direct were divided into two blocks and the papers that appeared as results in the two searches (Query 1 and Query 2 in Appendix I) were used, i.e. the results of the

search in this database were those that were duplicated when the both searches were combined and, therefore, met all the requirements.

The search fields corresponding to each article were used, which included the title, abstract and keywords specified by the author(s) in the documents, with variations depending on the utilised database. The whole document search was utilised for the conceptual groupings referring to sustainability. Field searches were similar in Scopus, WoS and Science Direct, with the combination of the 'TITLE-ABS-KEY' tags in Scopus, 'TS' in WOS and the 'Title, abstract or author-specified keywords' field in the advanced Science Direct search. In both WoS and Scopus, the 'AND ALL' tag was applied to add the search in the entire document. For Science Direct, the advanced search field 'Find articles with these terms' was filled in. The case of Pro Quest and IEEE Xplore differed because the title, abstract and keywords fields were separated. Therefore in Pro Quest, tags 'ti' (title), 'abs' (abstract) and 'fi' (identifier, keywords) were used, but no tag was employed to search the whole document. Finally with IEEE Xplore, fields 'Document Title', 'Abstract', 'Author Keywords' and, to search the whole text, 'Full Text & Metadata', were applied.

As previously mentioned, the full-text search for words referring to sustainability yielded diffuse results in this context. This is because the full-text search includes the references section. So there were results that had no indication of sustainability throughout the text, but the word appeared in some references. This setback was solved during the third filtering of the results for being more in-depth filtering and an exhaustive search was carried out for the sustainability concepts in papers' contents. Appendix I shows the different search queries for each database.

A frame window was considered from 2012 because I4.0 was first defined in 2011 (Kagermann, Wahlster, and Helbig 2013) to the present-day. Furthermore, the I5.0 concept is more recent, but focusing on human beings has been possible in the last few years without specifically naming I5.0. With Scopus, WoS, ScienceDirect and IEEE Xplore, the set time window was between 1 January 2012 and the present-day, and the option of article consultation from 2012 was added. With ProQuest, the 'After date' filter option was chosen in the 'Date of publication' section for the search by command. This means that the same time window as in the other databases was covered.

The types of documents considered during searches were those mainly selected and included in the filter journal articles, conference articles and reviews. The filters to choose them depending on databases were: in Scopus, the labels for document types 'article' and

'review' were selected; in WoS, document types 'proceedings paper', 'article' and 'review article' were chosen. During the Science Direct search, this was refined with article types 'Review articles' and 'Research articles'. The ProQuest search was limited to 'Peer-reviewed articles' from 'Scientific journals' and 'Professional journals', and document types 'Main article' and 'Article'. Finally, the IEEE Xplore search was filtered by 'Subscribed Content' and document type 'journals'.

Regarding the improvement of document searches by subject area, in Scopus the results were filtered by limiting them to subject areas 'Engineering', 'Computer Science', 'Business, Management and Accounting', 'Mathematics', 'Decision Sciences', 'Economics, Econometrics and Finance' and 'Multidisciplinary'. With WoS, the search was refined with categories 'Engineering', 'Computer Science', 'Science Technology Other Topics', 'Operations Research Management Science', 'Business Economics', 'Mathematics', 'Robotics' and 'Automation Control Systems'. Finally for subject areas, the case of Science Direct is mentioned because ProQuest and IEEE Xplore do not have this filtering tool. Similarly with Science Direct, subject labels 'Engineering', 'Decision Sciences', 'Computer Science', 'Business, Management and Accounting' and 'Mathematics' were chosen.

As **Error! Reference source not found.** depicts, the parallel step to the various database searches was to set up alerts for databases to, thus, continue to collect articles from databases until the present-day. Based on the collected documents, the next step was to automatically discard duplicates with the Jabref tool by performing searches in consecutive stages. Then a first review of all the collected articles was carried out to: (i) eliminate possible duplicates that the tool had not recognised due to the export method of each record according to the database; (ii) discard documents in which the used keywords had a different interpretation to that of the specified context; (iii) remove documents in which the language was not Spanish or English and it was not possible to obtain an official translation. This first filtering left 383 documents. From the alerts in the different databases, 117 extra documents were obtained after this first filtering by the same method. This first filtering yielded 500 documents (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The second filtering process was carried out by reading the titles of each document that passed the first filtering by discarding those whose study subject differed from that of the present research. From this second filtering process, 151 documents from the main search and 46 documents from alerts remained. Therefore, the second filtering yielded 197 documents for review purposes. They were then subjected to the third filtering, which involved a

thorough reading of the abstracts and conclusions of each document, as well as a brief analysis of the critical contents of each document. During this process, the following were discarded: (i) those with academic contributions that did not align with the research context; (ii) those documents that did not include sustainability aspects throughout the text, but only in their references. In the end, 77 documents (**Error! Reference source not found.**) were selected from the main search and the documents collected by alerts, whose titles and authors are listed in Table 2.

Of the selected documents, the earliest dated documents are from 2018. It should be noted that the time window of the search covered from 2012, but of the 151 papers that passed the second filtering (**Error! Reference source not found.**), only two were from 2015, and five from 2017. Therefore, the relevant literature within the research framework that concerns us began to stand out in 2018. It is noteworthy that it was not until 2016 that the I4.0 concept contemplated the importance of environmental sustainability from laws, such as the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC 2015). Accordingly, greenhouse gas emissions caused by human activities are contributing to global warming and to the deterioration of climate and environmental ecology (Tsai and Lu 2018). It is worth noting that the relevant literature within the research framework increased considerably in 2021 and continued to grow in 2022, accounting for almost 60% of the selected articles between these two years. Regarding the publications of 2023 collected through alerts, 12 publications were identified.

Table 2. Selected documents.

	Author/s	Document title
1	Abderrahim et al. (2020)	Manufacturing 4.0 operations scheduling with AGV battery management constraints
2	Abidi, Mohammed, and Alkhalefah (2022)	Predictive maintenance planning for industry 4.0 using machine learning for sustainable manufacturing
3	Agostino et al. (2020)	Dynamic production order allocation for distributed additive manufacturing
4	Akkad and Bányai (2023)	Energy consumption optimization of milk-run-based in-plant supply solutions: an industry 4.0 approach
5	Amjad, Rafique, and Khan (2021)	Leveraging optimized and cleaner production through industry 4.0
6	Awad and Abd-Elaziz (2021)	A new perspective for solving manufacturing scheduling based problems respecting new data considerations
7	Aydin and Tirkolaei (2022)	A systematic review of aggregate production planning literature with an outlook for sustainability and circularity
8	Bakon et al. (2022)	Scheduling under uncertainty for industry 4.0 and 5.0
9	Bányai (2021)	Optimization of material supply in smart manufacturing environment: a metaheuristic approach for matrix production
10	Bányai et al. (2019)	Optimization of municipal waste collection routing: impact of industry 4.0 technologies on environmental awareness and sustainability
11	Battini et al. (2022)	Towards industry 5.0: a multi-objective job rotation model for an inclusive workforce

	Author/s	Document title
12	Bortolini et al. (2022)	A three-objective optimization model for mid-term sustainable supply chain network design
13	Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog (2023)	Assembly line optimization using MTM time standard and simulation modeling—a case study
14	Chen, Lee Kong, and Kan (2023)	Identifying the promising production planning and scheduling method for manufacturing in Industry 4.0: a literature review
15	Demartini et al. (2021)	A review of production planning models: emerging features and limitations compared to practical implementation
16	Dunke et al. (2018)	Time traps in supply chains: is optimal still good enough?
17	Esteso et al. (2022)	Reinforcement learning applied to production planning and control
18	Farooq et al. (2021)	Supply chain operations management in pandemics: a state-of-the-art review inspired by COVID-19
19	Goienetxea Uriarte, Ng, and Urenda Moris (2020)	Bringing together lean and simulation: a comprehensive review
20	Groten and Gallego-García (2021)	A systematic improvement model to optimize production systems within industry 4.0 environments: a simulation case study
21	Himmiche et al. (2023)	Robustness evaluation process for scheduling under uncertainties
22	Iqbal et al. (2022)	Enhanced time-constraint aware tasks scheduling mechanism based on predictive optimization for efficient load balancing in smart manufacturing
23	Ivanov et al. (2018)	A survey on control theory applications to operational systems, supply chain management, and industry 4.0
24	Jiang, Zhang, and Wang (2023)	Grid-map-based path planning and task assignment for multi-type AGVs in a distribution warehouse
25	Jong et al. (2020)	The multi-layered job-shop automatic scheduling system of mould manufacturing for industry 3.5
26	Khettabi, Benyoucef, and Amine Boutiche (2022)	Sustainable multi-objective process planning in reconfigurable manufacturing environment: adapted new dynamic NSGA-II vs new NSGA-III
27	Krenczyk and Paprocka (2023)	Integration of discrete simulation, prediction, and optimization methods for a production line digital twin design
28	Kuik and Diong (2019)	A model-driven decision approach to collaborative planning and obsolescence for manufacturing operations
29	Kumar, Singh, and Lamba (2018)	Sustainable robust layout using big data approach: a key towards industry 4.0
30	Leite, Pinto, and Alves (2019)	A real-time optimization algorithm for the integrated planning and scheduling problem towards the context of industry 4.0
31	Leng et al. (2022)	Blockchained smart contract pyramid-driven multi-agent autonomous process control for resilient individualised manufacturing towards industry 5.0
32	Leong et al. (2020)	Enhancing the adaptability: lean and green strategy towards the industry revolution 4.0
33	Li (2021)	An algorithm for arranging operators to balance assembly lines and reduce operator training time
34	Li and Huang (2021)	Production-intralogistics synchronization of industry 4.0 flexible assembly lines under graduation intelligent manufacturing system
35	Li and Wang (2022)	A review of green shop scheduling problem
36	Li et al. (2020)	Machine learning and optimization for production rescheduling in industry 4.0
37	Li et al. (2022)	Survey of integrated flexible job shop scheduling problems
38	Li, Tan, and Li (2018)	Research on dynamic facility layout problem of manufacturing unit considering human factors
39	Lind et al. (2023)	Virtual-simulation-based multi-objective optimization of an assembly station in a battery production factory
40	Maheshwari et al. (2023)	Digital twin-driven real-time planning, monitoring, and controlling in food supply chains
41	Mirabelli and Solina (2022)	Optimization strategies for the integrated management of perishable supply chains: a literature review
42	Mohammadi et al. (2023)	Industry 4.0 in waste management: An integrated IoT-based approach for facility location and green vehicle routing
43	Mula and Bogataj (2021)	OR in the industrial engineering of industry 4.0: experiences from the Iberian Peninsula mirrored in CJOR.
44	Muñoz-Villamizar et al. (2021)	Toolkit for simultaneously improving production and environmental efficiencies
45	Naderi et al. (2019)	Sustainable operations management for industry 4.0 and its social return

Author/s	Document title
46 Nguyen et al. (2022)	Data analytics in pharmaceutical supply chains: state of the art, opportunities, and challenges
47 Para, Del Ser, and Nebro (2022)	Energy-aware multi-objective job shop scheduling optimization with metaheuristics in manufacturing industries: a critical survey, results, and perspectives
48 Pawar and Bhosale (2022)	Flexible job shop scheduling for press working industries with operation precedence constraint
49 Pires et al. (2018)	Towards a simulation-based optimization approach to integrate supply chain planning and control
50 Pires, Parreira, and Frazzon (2021)	Integrated operational supply chain planning in industry 4.0
51 Rahman et al. (2021)	Flowshop scheduling with sequence dependent setup times and batch delivery in supply chain
52 Ramadan et al. (2020)	Industry 4.0-based real-time scheduling and dispatching in lean manufacturing systems
53 Ramakurthi et al. (2022)	An innovative approach for resource sharing and scheduling in a sustainable distributed manufacturing system
54 Rega et al. (2021)	Collaborative workplace design: a knowledge-based approach to promote human-robot collaboration and multi-objective layout optimization
55 Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic (2021)	Design guideline for flexible industrial buildings integrating industry 4.0 parameters
56 Salama and Eltawil (2018)	A decision support system architecture based on simulation optimization for cyber-physical systems
57 Santos et al. (2022)	Many-objective optimization of a three-echelon supply chain: a case study in the pharmaceutical industry
58 Sar and Ghadimi (2022)	Designing reverse logistics network for a case study of home-care health medical device waste management: implications for industry 4.0 supply chains
59 Schwemmer et al. (2023)	Workforce rostering for decentrally controlled production systems: a simulation-based optimization framework using a genetic algorithm
60 Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler (2021a)	Smart manufacturing scheduling: a literature review
61 Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler (2021b)	Smart master production schedule for the supply chain: a conceptual framework
62 Tabatabaei et al. (2021)	A novel framework for storage assignment optimization inspired by finite element method
63 Takeda-Berger et al. (2022)	Reactive production scheduling approach based on inventory availability
64 Tan et al. (2023)	Scheduling and controlling production in an internet of things environment for industry 4.0: an analysis and systematic review of scientific metrological data
65 Tripathi et al. (2021a)	An agile system to enhance productivity through a modified value stream mapping approach in industry 4.0: a novel approach
66 Tripathi et al. (2021b)	An innovative agile model of smart lean-green approach for sustainability enhancement in industry 4.0
67 Tripathi et al. (2022a)	Development of a data-driven decision-making system using lean and smart manufacturing concept in industry 4.0: a case study
68 Tripathi et al. (2022b)	A novel smart production management system for the enhancement of industrial sustainability in industry 4.0
69 Trstenjak et al. (2022)	Logistics 5.0 implementation model based on decision support systems
70 Tsai and Lu (2018)	A framework of production planning and control with carbon tax under industry 4.0
71 Yazdi, Azizi, and Hashemipour (2019)	A hybrid methodology for validation of optimization solutions effects on manufacturing sustainability with time study and simulation approach for SMEs
72 YounesSinaki et al. (2022)	Cellular manufacturing design 1996–2021: a review and introduction to applications of industry 4.0
73 Yu (2022)	Modeling a remanufacturing reverse logistics planning problem: some insights into disruptive technology adoption
74 Zhang et al. (2021)	Optimizing medical enterprise's operations management considering corporate social responsibility under industry 5.0
75 Zhang et al. (2022)	Dynamic scheduling method for job-shop manufacturing systems by deep reinforcement learning with proximal policy optimization
76 Zhang et al. (2023)	An efficient metaheuristic algorithm for job shop scheduling in a dynamic environment

	Author/s	Document title
77	Zhou et al. (2022)	Production and operations management for intelligent manufacturing: a systematic literature review

Of the total number of documents that passed the third filtering, 77, i.e. 78% were journal articles, 12% were journal reviews and one was a journal short survey, all of which were published in indexed journals, while seven documents were conference papers. Of the selected articles, the contributions of the Sustainability Journal with 10 publications and the International Journal of Production Research with seven publications stood out. The contributions from these two journals accounted for 22% of the total. Other significant contributions to the selected literature were the references in Applied Sciences and Computers & Industrial Engineering with five publications each. The outstanding contributions of IFAC-PapersOnLine, Mathematical Problems in Engineering and Processes, respectively with four, three and three publications, were also taken into account. Of these, the last one accounted for 20% of the chosen articles, i.e. 42% of the total number of papers for the literature review came from the journals mentioned in this paragraph.

3. Literature review

The 77 selected documents were then reviewed by a thematic, content and taxonomic analysis.

3.1 Thematic analysis

An analysis of keyword co-occurrences was carried out using the bibliographic records of the documents filtered through the methodology and the VOSviewer software version 1.6.2019. Before creating the map, a thesaurus was created from the 341 found keywords and 211 keywords were finally considered. Figure 2 shows the relations among keywords, symbolised by co-occurrence networks. A minimum number of co-occurrences of one keyword was taken into account so that it would appear in the network of three co-occurrences. Thus after using the thesaurus, and given the restriction of the minimum of three co-occurrences, 40 keywords appear on the map, which are, therefore, the most treated topics in this literature review.

The most recurrent focus in the literature review was I4.0, which heads a group (coloured in blue in Figure 2) that includes the IoT, integration and LM. The next group in red is led by the optimisation concept, with a network of co-occurrences with manufacturing, machine learning and people. Heading the third block (green) are keywords simulation and supply chain, which relate to concepts like multi-objective optimisation and metaheuristics, and come over as relevant in literature reviews. Finally, a fourth group (yellow) links the sustainability and scheduling concepts with themes of decision support systems and smart manufacturing.

Figure 3 shows how both I4.0 and optimisation have co-occurrences with most of the other analysed concepts, which makes them the fundamental pillars of this literature review. The sustainability concept is related to fewer keywords, but also presents many co-occurrences. Compared to the topics mentioned in the first section, the people concept appears in the network of the I4.0 concept and also in the network of the optimisation and sustainability concept. The social concepts are also related to the manufacturing, multi-objective optimisation, simulation and I5.0 concepts.

3.2 Content analysis

In order to analyse the content of the articles selected in this review, and based on Díaz-Madroñero, Mula, and Peidro (2014) and Mula et al. (2010), a classification scheme is proposed by selecting those general criteria and extending with new specific criteria that focus on the research objective. The criteria and classification categories to be taken into account are detailed below:

(i) Research methodology: it refers to the set of methods and techniques used to conduct scientific research. Different methodological approaches can be distinguished, such as conceptual, descriptive, empirical, cross-sectional exploratory and longitudinal exploratory, or their combinations (Dangayach and Deshmukh 2001)

(ii) Economic activities and (iii) industry sector: each research work is given a category from The International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) system, which is used to classify economic activities and the sector of each article (Rojas, Mula, and Sanchis 2023)

(iv) Contribution/objectives/purpose: the objective(s) defined in the research that represent(s) the main study contribution, the aims and goals pursued by the work

(v) Problem: it refers to the nature of the problem addressed in research. The following problems are distinguished in research: APP, master production scheduling (MPS), material requirements planning (MRP), transport planning (supply), production assignment, production scheduling, production sequencing, inventory management, distribution planning (customers), supply chain network design, facility resource planning and capacity planning

(vi) Problem naming: it specifies the name by which the research author refers to the problem

(vii) Application context: it presents the context in which each proposal is carried out, these being supply chain contexts, in which problems are considered that are influenced by factors of all (or several) of those involved in the supply chain and manufacturing and assembly company contexts, where problems that specifically affect a company (only one link in the supply chain) are considered

(viii) Decision level: the three decision levels are strategical, tactical and operational, and correspond to long-term, mid-term and short-term periods (Mula et al. 2010)

(ix) SCOR process: the reviewed problems are classified according to the supply chain operations reference (SCOR) model (Stewart 1997) into source, make and deliver plans and their combinations

(x) Modelling and solution approach. It consists of the type of representation and the aspects or considered algorithms to solve the proposed models. It can be conceptual framework, heuristic, LM techniques, machine learning, manufacturing strategies, mathematical programming, metaheuristic, simulation, among others

(xi) Model and method. It refers specifically to the methods and algorithms used to solve the proposed models. It may include the exact name of algorithms, metaheuristics and problem-specific heuristics

(xii) Development/software tools. This refers to the commercial or non-commercial software tools required to implement and solve the proposed models

(xiii) I4.0 technology. This refers to the technologies associated with I4.0 that are used to implement the proposed models. The considered technologies are: additive manufacturing, AI, automation and robotics, blockchain, cloud computing, CPS, cybersecurity, data analytics and big data, the IoT and sensors, simulation and digital twin (DT), extended reality and tracking and tracing systems

(xiv) Focus on I5.0. It refers to approaches associated with I5.0 used to implement the proposed models or are taken into account in their conception or conclusions. They focus on human-machine collaboration by encouraging interaction and cooperation between humans and machines

(xv) Focus on people. This is about the consideration of human and social aspects in the design and implementation of the proposed models by prioritising the well-being and participation of the involved people

(xvi) Sustainability approaches, circular economy and reverse and green manufacturing: they provide details as to whether the study takes into account environmental, economic and social sustainability approaches, or their combinations, to develop a solution

(xvii) Benefits/novelty. Here the main features of the model/research that outperform other existing scientific research are stated by highlighting the provided benefits and novelty that have been identified by the author(s)

(xviii) Limitations/challenges/further research. These identify the characteristics that limit the application of the model/research to particular settings, as well as the challenges and areas for further research that have been identified by the author(s)

More details of how articles were classified can be found in Appendices II, III, IV, V and VI.

3.2.1 Objectives

The main objectives of the selected articles are summarised in Table 3 and more details can be found in Appendix II. Of these objectives, the most important ones are the development and validation of models, followed by the proposal and implementation of management strategies and the evaluation of models' performance for specific problems. Finally, literature reviews and analyses of the implementation of specific I4.0 tools are also considered.

Research coincides with the search for sustainable solutions that improve industrial systems' efficiency and resilience through PPC. Table 3 shows the wide variety of problems addressed in the literature. However, some trends come over; for example, several papers focus on improving energy efficiency (Ramakurthi et al. 2022) and sustainability by reflecting growing concern for the environmental (Bortolini et al. 2022), economic and social (Naderi et al. 2019) impacts of operations. Another trend focuses on supply chains' resilience (Farooq et al. 2021) and adaptability, particularly in the event

of disruptive events (Nguyen et al. 2022) like the COVID-19 pandemic, which has tested the stability of these global networks to adapt them in these scenarios. Some studies focus on uncertainty management (Bakon et al. 2022) and planning under changing conditions (Dunke et al. 2018), and underline the importance of developing robust strategies that can be adapted quickly to market variations. Of all the objectives, we also stress the importance of the time factor: completion time, lead time, value-added time, real-time, time traps or timelines.

Table 3. Main objectives of the selected articles.

Objectives	Number of articles
Development and validation of models	27
Proposal and implementation of management strategies	19
Performance evaluation of models	12
Review and analysis of the literature	11
Implementation of I4.0 tools	8

3.2.2 Application contexts

Application contexts are classified based on the ISIC. The analysed articles come mainly from manufacturing contexts, with some contributions from other fields, such as construction, energy supply, transport and storage of materials and waste management. Table 4 contains the economic activities and sectors of the analysed items, while Appendix II provides more details about each individual item. However, some analysed articles describe a general manufacturing environment rather than a specific industry sector. It is also important to note that 35 of the 77 reviewed articles, as listed in Appendix II, contain case studies, which make real-world applications noteworthy.

Table 4. Economic activities and sectors of the analysed documents.

Economic activities	Sector	Number of articles
Manufacturing	Manufacturing	39
	Machinery	8
	Parts and accessories for motor vehicles	5
	Food products	5
	Rubber and plastic products	4
	Electrical equipment	4
	Pharmaceuticals products	2
	Pressing of metals	1
	Air and spacecraft and related machinery	1
Construction		2
Transportation and storage		2
Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities	Waste collection	3
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	Electric power generation, transmission and distribution	1

The studies from the general manufacturing activities sector stand out, followed by specific sectors that produce machinery, parts and accessories for motor vehicles, food products and rubber and plastic products. Manufacturing sectors like electrical equipment, mainly household appliances, pharmaceuticals, metallurgy and machines related to the aviation and space sectors, are scarcely addressed. The automotive sector (and by extension, the rubber sector) is, like the food sector, one of the fastest evolving sectors in terms of optimisation models, sustainability and I4.0 tools use. In this group of manufacturing activities, contexts in which advanced technologies like automated guided vehicles (AGVs) (Abderrahim et al. 2020) and cellular manufacturing (YounesSinaki et al. 2022) are implemented, and specific components are produced by specialised techniques, such as injection moulding (Jong et al. 2020) and remanufacturing practices (Yu 2022) stand out. In addition, environments include epidemic outbreaks in supply chains (Farooq et al. 2021), the search for adaptability in dynamic environments (Takeda-Berger et al. 2022) or the management of perishable products (Mirabelli and Solina 2022) and pharmaceutical supply chains (Nguyen et al. 2022).

Manufacturing industry-specific optimisation techniques are also addressed in other application sectors, such as construction, transport and storage, waste collection and energy production and distribution. In this way, they are adapted to specific contexts to improve their efficiency. In the construction field, the aim is to use I4.0 tools to flexibly generate industrial buildings (Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic 2021). In the transportation sector, the aim is to improve transport and distribution routes, or transport in plants in smart manufacturing and I4.0 environments, as in Bányai (2021), and also in waste management that focuses on optimising collection routes.

Sectors like pharmaceuticals, textiles and electronics also appear in Table 4. These are vital sectors in which optimisation, sustainability strategies and I4.0 tools play a key role in improving PPC and can evolve towards more sustainable and people-centred I5.0.

3.2.3 Research methodologies

Articles are classified according to their research methodology, as shown in Figure 4. Here the most widely used research methodology by 64.9% of the articles is the empirical one. The next most used research methodology is the conceptual, with models and literature reviews accounting for 20.8% of cases, followed by the descriptive, that represent only 5.2% of the articles. Finally, methodologies that combine exploratory

approached with conceptual and empirical ones, or a combination of the last two, are the least used by the analysed articles.

Figure 4 Caption. Research methodology of the selected documents.

Figure 4 Alt Text. Pie chart depicting the research methodologies of the selected documents with empirical (64.9%), conceptual (20.8%) and descriptive (5.2%) studies, and fewer combined methods like empirical-exploratory cross-sectional ones (3.9%).

3.2.4 Type of problem

Table 5 details the application context, the decision level, the SCOR process and the type of problems of the reviewed articles. Most focus on manufacturing and assembly companies. Specifically, 61% of the papers refer to cases in this context. It is important to highlight the nine contributions in the facility resource planning problem, which corresponds to a strategic level that addresses the optimisation of assembly lines and facility layouts by using simulation (Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog 2023; Yazdi, Azizi, and Hashemipour 2019), mathematical models and metaheuristics (Kumar, Singh, and Lamba 2018; YounesSinaki et al. 2022) by considering safety, sustainability, lean and green strategies (Leong et al. 2020; Lind et al. 2023), efficiency and costs (Li, Tan, and Li 2018). Another paper addresses this problem, which stands out at the strategical and operational levels (Naderi et al. 2019).

We also note that the production scheduling problem is highlighted at not only the strategical level but, and above all, also at the operational level, and less so at the tactical level, with a total of 38% of the references to the problem in a manufacturing context. These articles develop mathematical models, real-time optimisation algorithms and work rotation schemes by considering ergonomics and welfare. Lean, green and technological strategies are integrated to reduce production times and emissions. Another focus lies on

the flexible and sustainable scheduling of assembly lines employing deep learning methods and metaheuristic algorithms. Other less numerous problems in the selected literature for this manufacturing context are: APP (Tsai and Lu 2018), considered also with MPS (Chen, Lee Kong, and Kan 2023); production assignment, which appears alone (Awad and Abd-Elaziz 2021; Jiang, Zhang, and Wang 2023; Li 2021) and is also combined with production sequencing (Leite, Pinto, and Alves 2019); inventory management (Tabatabaei et al. 2021), which also appears combined with production scheduling (Leng et al. 2022).

In the supply chain context, we find that 26% of the articles in which problems are once again associated with production scheduling stand out. Nine references mix this with other problems, such as inventory management and distribution scheduling (Pires et al. 2018; Pires, Parreira, and Frazzon 2021; Rahman et al. 2021; Agostino et al. 2020). It is essential to highlight the problems that are only identified in this context, which are those of supply chain network designs from strategical (Bortolini et al. 2022; Groten and Gallego-García 2021; Mohammadi et al. 2023) and operational (Zhang et al. 2021) points of view. Inventory management and distribution scheduling are also problems that appear in other contexts, but in the supply chain they are studied together by Mirabelli and Solina (2022), Pires et al. (2018), Pires, Parreira, and Frazzon (2021) and Yu (2022). In their industrial solution, APP, MPS and MRP are some of the problems that Demartini et al. (2021) examine. Also, we find other examples of MRP in Kuik and Diong (2019) and Santos et al. (2022). Regarding the transport problem, Sar and Ghadimi (2022) study the reverse logistic network to manage medical product waste.

In the supply chain and manufacturing contexts, descriptive (Ivanov et al. 2018) and conceptual (Esteso et al. 2022; Mula and Bogataj 2021; Zhou et al. 2022) approaches address a variety of problems, while the cross-sectional and empirical exploratory study by Trstenjak et al. (2022) considers facility resource planning to develop a decision support system to implement logistics 5.0. The empirical study by Maheshwari et al. (2023) integrates a DT model to optimise procurement, production and distribution in food processing. Finally, the APP research by Aydin and Tirkolaei (2022), the production scheduling problems by Bakon et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2022), and the literature review of the combination of lean and simulation by Goienetxea Uriarte, Ng and Urenda Moris (2020) do not indicate any specific performance or study context. Further details on the problems analysed by each author come in Appendix III.

Table 5. Classification of problem types

Context	Decision level			SCOR process			Problem type											Authors	
	Strategical	Tactical	Operational	Source	Make	Delivery	APP	MPS	MRP	TP	PA	PSH	PSQ	IM	DS	SCN	FRP		CP
-	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•							Goienetxea Uriarte, Ng, and Urenda Moris (2020) Aydin and Tirkolaei (2022) Bakon et al. (2022), Li et al. (2022)
Manufacturing	•	•	•	•	•	•	•										•		Tsai and Lu (2018) YounesSinaki et al. (2022), Yazdi, Azizi, and Hashemipour (2019), Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic (2021), Rega et al. (2021), Li, Tan, and Li (2018), Leong et al. (2020), Kumar, Singh, and Lamba (2018), Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog (2023), Lind et al. (2023) Tripathi et al. (2021b), Tripathi et al. (2022a), Tripathi et al. (2022b), Himmiche et al. (2023) Tripathi et al. (2021a) Li (2021) Abidi, Mohammed, and Alkhalefah (2022) Muñoz-Villamizar et al. (2021) Leite, Pinto, and Alves (2019) Chen, Lee Kong, and Kan (2023) Jiang, Zhang, and Wang (2023) Tabatabaei et al. (2021) Awad and Abd-Elaziz (2021) Abderrahim et al. (2020), Akkad and Bányai (2023), Amjad, Rafique, and Khan (2021), Bányai (2021), Battini et al. (2022), Iqbal et al. (2022), Jong et al. (2020), Li and Huang (2021), Li and Wang (2022), Zhang et al. (2022), Para, Del Ser, and Nebro (2022), Pawar and Bhosale (2022), Ramadan et al. (2020), Tan et al. (2023), Li et al. (2020), Krenczyk and Paprocka (2023), Schwemmer et al. (2023), Zhang et al. (2023) Takeda-Berger et al. (2022) Ramakurthi et al. (2022) Leng et al. (2022) Khettabi, Benyoucef, and Amine Boutiche (2022) Naderi et al. (2019) Salama and Eltawil (2018)
SC	•	•	•	•	•	•												•	Bortolini et al. (2022) Nguyen et al. (2022) Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler (2021b) Groten and Gallego-García (2021) Mohammadi et al. (2023) Farooq et al. (2021) Zhang et al. (2021) Kuik and Diong (2019) Yu (2022) Demartini et al. (2021) Dunke et al. (2018)

Context	Decision level			SCOR process			Problem type										Authors		
	Strategical	Tactical	Operational	Source	Make	Delivery	APP	MPS	MRP	TP	PA	PSH	PSQ	IM	DS	SCN		FRP	CP
			•	•	•	•						•		•	•				Pires, Parreira, and Frazzon (2021) Pires et al. (2018) Santos et al. (2022) Rahman et al. (2021) Agostino et al. (2020) Sar and Ghadimi (2022) Bányai et al. (2019) Mirabelli and Solina (2022) Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler (2021a)
SC+Manufacturing	•	•	•	•	•	•												•	Trstenjak et al. (2022) Maheshwari et al. (2023) Ivanov et al. (2018) Zhou et al. (2022) Mula and Bogataj (2021) Esteso et al. (2022)

Note: aggregate production planning (APP); master production scheduling (MPS); material requirements planning (MRP); transport planning (supply) (TP); production assignment (PA); production scheduling (PSH); production sequencing (PSQ); inventory management (IM); distribution scheduling (customers) (DS); supply chain network design (SCN); facility resource planning (FRP); capacity planning (CP).

3.2.5 Modelling and solution approaches

Modelling and solution approaches are divided into ten groups: conceptual framework, heuristic, LM techniques, machine learning, manufacturing strategies, mathematical programming, metaheuristic, simulation, statistical analysis and others.

Conceptual framework modelling approaches are the least represented, with only two contributions: the guideline for integrated industrial building design by Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic (2021); smart MPS by Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler (2021b).

Ten articles employ heuristics. The agile model for process optimisation or the agile system to enhance productivity by Tripathi et al. (2021a) and Tripathi et al. (2021b), respectively. Li (2021) utilises the cluster algorithm, Leite, Pinto, and Alves (2019) design a constructive heuristic, while Tripathi et al. (2022a) develop a heuristic for a data-driven decision making system. The production assignment problem of Jiang, Zhang, and Wang (2023) applies the A-star algorithm with a cyclic rule to solve the path planning model and it finds the shortest path for AGVs. The framework by Demartini et al. (2021) considers decomposition and aggregation heuristics, as well as greedy heuristics, as solution approaches. Bortolini et al. (2022) use the normalised normal constraint method to obtain the Pareto frontier of the solution for the supply chain network (SCN) design problem. Ramadan et al. (2020) create a method for a real-time dispatching system and Tripathi et al. (2022b) report a smart management system for enhancing industrial

sustainability. Finally, Li and Huang (2021) include a Graph-Theory-based clustering for planning and scheduling in real time and real-time decentralised ticketing for the execution/control of a queueing process.

The LM techniques applied by nine of the selected models from the literature are the Lean and Green Index (LGI) (Leong et al. 2020) as a benchmarking and monitoring tool for operational improvement, the LM approach itself (Groten and Gallego-García 2021; Tripathi et al. 2021b; 2022a; 2022b), the six sigma (6S) methodology (Groten and Gallego-García 2021; Tripathi et al. 2022a), total productive maintenance (TPM) (Amjad, Rafique, and Khan 2021) principles and, finally, value stream mapping (VSM) (Muñoz-Villamizar et al. 2021; Ramadan et al. 2020; Tripathi et al. 2021a).

Next six articles apply machine learning to modelling or solving problems. Several techniques are applied in these articles: adaptive gradient algorithm, adaptive moment estimation, autoregressive neural networks, deep neural network, deep RL, multilayer perceptrons, predictive optimisation, proximal policy optimisation, random forest classifier, recurrent neural network, stochastic gradient descent and support vector machines.

There are five empirical studies that employ manufacturing strategies. Groten and Gallego-García (2021) study the introduction of quick response manufacturing (QRM) and agile manufacturing (AM) in a supply chain context. Regarding application contexts in companies, Tripathi et al. (2021a), Tripathi et al. (2022b) and Tripathi et al. (2022b) introduce smart manufacturing strategies, while Amjad, Rafique and Khan (2021) implement the 6R technique (reuse, reduce, recycle, recover, redesign and re-manufacture).

Mathematical programming approaches are widely used in the selected literature, with 27 references, which include models that attend to the classification of: binary linear programming, integer linear programming (ILP), mixed integer linear programming (MILP), non-linear programming (NLP), integer non-linear programming (INLP), mixed integer non-linear programming (MINLP), multi-objective linear programming (MOLP), multi-objective mixed integer linear programming (MOMILP), multi-objective integer non-linear programming (MOINLP); multi-objective mixed integer non-linear programming (MOMINLP) and ε -constraint algorithms.

Another approach that is also widely used, specifically in 27 studies, is metaheuristics, which solves various types of problems. The metaheuristics found in these studies include the following algorithms: ant colony optimisation (ACO), binary bat

optimisation algorithm, black-hole, differential evolution, discrete artificial bee colony with k means clustering, flower pollination, general variable neighbourhood search algorithm, genetic algorithm, heuristic kalman algorithm, hybridised moth flame evolutionary optimisation algorithm, improved artificial bee colony with particle swarm optimisation, improved multiphase particle swarm optimisation, improved variable neighbourhood tabu search, jaya algorithm and sea lion optimisation, keshtel algorithm, lévy flight moth flame optimisation, multi-objective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition, moth flame optimisation, new dynamic non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm, non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (Pareto-based), particle swarm optimisation, social engineering optimisation, surrogate modelling-evolutionary multiobjective optimisation algorithm, simulated annealing, tabu search, time constraint aware and variable neighbourhood descent algorithm.

Twenty papers include simulation approaches, with approaches based on agent-based simulation and multi-agent simulation (Leng et al. 2022; Maheshwari et al. 2023; Yazdi, Azizi, and Hashemipour 2019). In discrete event simulation, there are simulations of the facility resource planning problem, with the simulation of assembly lines (Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog 2023), assembly stations (Lind et al. 2023) or production lines (Naderi et al. 2019), and also simulations of the production scheduling problem with workshop simulation (Himmiche et al. 2023), simulation of schedules (Krenczyk and Paprocka 2023), simulation models (Salama and Eltawil 2018; Zhang et al. 2023) and simulation-based optimisation (Schwemmer et al. 2023; Takeda-Berger et al. 2022). In addition, Tabatabaei et al. (2021) follow the finite element method to manage inventory. Groten and Gallego-García (2021), Pires et al. (2018) and Ramadan et al. (2020) use system dynamics modelling, while Yu (2022) solves an optimisation model with sample average approximation, and Amjad, Rafique and Khan (2021) propose the improvements of their study with a spreadsheet.

Statistical analyses are represented in nine of the selected papers, of which the ANOVA analysis (Amjad, Rafique, and Khan 2021; Rega et al. 2021; Tripathi et al. 2022a) and the statistical comparative analysis (Tripathi et al. 2021a; 2021b; 2022b) are the most frequently used. However, autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA), exponential smoothing, the Friedman test ranking method, interpretive ranking process, simple multi-attribute rating technique (SMART) and statistical model checking also appear.

Table 6. Modelling and solution approaches.

Conceptual framework	Guideline for integrated industrial building design Smart master production schedule		Ant colony optimisation Binary bat optimisation algorithm Black-hole Differential evolution algorithm Discrete artificial bee colony algorithm with k-means clustering Flower pollination General variable neighbourhood search algorithm Genetic algorithm Heuristic Kalman algorithm Hybridised moth flame evolutionary optimisation algorithm (HMFE0) Improved artificial bee colony with particle swarm optimisation Improved multiphase particle swarm optimisation Improved variable neighbourhood tabu search Jaya algorithm and sea lion optimisation Keshtel algorithm Lévy flight moth flame optimisation Multi-objective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition Moth flame optimisation New dynamic non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm Non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (Pareto-based) Particle swarm optimisation Social engineering optimisation Surrogate modelling-evolutionary multi-objective optimisation algorithm Simulated annealing Tabu search Time constraint aware Variable neighbourhood descent algorithm
Heuristic	A-star algorithm Agile model for process optimisation Agile system to enhance productivity Cluster algorithm Constructive heuristic Data-driven decision-making system Decomposition and aggregation heuristics Greedy heuristic Normalised normal constraint method Real time dispatching system Smart management system for the enhancement of industrial sustainability Graph Theory-based clustering Real-time decentralised ticketing	Metaheuristic	
Lean manufacturing techniques	Lean and Green Index (LGI) Lean manufacturing (LM) Six sigma (6S) Total productive maintenance (TPM) Value stream mapping (VSM)		
Machine learning	Adaptive gradient algorithm Adaptive moment estimation Autoregressive neural networks Deep neural network Deep reinforcement learning Multilayer Perceptrons Predictive optimisation Proximal policy optimisation Random forest classifier Recurrent neural network Stochastic gradient descent Support vector machines		
Manufacturing strategies	6R (reuse, reduce, recycle, recover, redesign and re-manufacture) Agile manufacturing (AM) Quick response manufacturing (QRM) Smart manufacturing	Simulation	Agent-based simulation Discrete event simulation Finite element method Multi-agent simulation Sample average approximation Spreadsheet simulation System dynamics
Mathematical programming	Binary linear programming Integer linear programming (ILP) Mixed integer linear programming (MILP) Non-linear programming (NLP) Integer non-linear programming (INLP) Mixed integer non-linear programming (MINLP) Multi-objective linear programming (MOLP) Multi-objective mixed integer linear programming (MOMILP) Multi-objective integer non-linear programming (MOINLP) Multi-objective mixed integer non-linear programming (MOMINLP) ϵ -constraint algorithm	Statistical analysis	ANOVA analysis Autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) Exponential smoothing Friedman test ranking method Interpretive ranking process Simple multi-attribute rating technique (SMART) Statistical comparative analysis Statistical model checking
		Others	Technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS) Activity-based costing (ABC) Analytic hierarchy process Analytic network process Categorised parameter catalogue L9 Taguchi orthogonal array Life cycle analysis Multicriteria analysis Normalised vector method Root mean squared error (RMSE) Theory of Constraints (TOC)

Finally, some authors apply other approaches, techniques or tools in the selected literature, such as the technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS) or activity-based costing (ABC). Leong et al. (2020) and Trstenjak et al. (2022) employ the analytic hierarchy process, while other authors implement the analytic network process, categorised parameter catalogue, L9 Taguchi orthogonal array, life cycle analysis, multicriteria analysis, normalised vector method or root mean squared error (RMSE). Finally, Groten and Gallego-García (2021) and Tsai and Lu (2018) report Theory of Constraints (TOC) to improve productivity.

These groups can be explored with their associated models and methods in Table 6. The details of each article come in Appendix III.

3.2.6 Software tools

The software tools that appear in the selected literature (Figure 5) can be divided into seven groups: bibliography, data analytics, databases and information management, optimisation and solutions, programming languages and integrated development environments (IDEs), simulation, Web services and applications.

Two bibliographic tools, VOSViewer and CiteSpace, are mainly used in systematic literature reviews. VOSViewer is applied to perform co-occurrence analysis with various types of information displayed on the maps that it generates, such as font size, distances between keywords and different coloured lines, to assess the importance of keywords and the relations between them to identify research trends (Nguyen et al. 2022). CiteSpace also allows the identification of the keyword timeline (Li and Wang 2022) and other tools, such as author co-citation (Tan et al. 2023).

Regarding data analysis tools, we highlight the use of Matlab in the selected literature, which is also applied for coding, execution and simulation of models. Other data analysis tools are the EasyPlan and ExpertFit software. In terms of databases and information management, Microsoft®(MS) SQL Server, FISCO BCOS and the SAP manager are named in articles.

Optimisation and problem-solving tools are widely used by authors, most notably CPLEX, which generates optimal solutions for small data instances (Rahman et al. 2021) and has also been employed to compare its solutions to those of different metaheuristics as in Pawar and Bhosale (2022), Ramakurthi et al. (2022) or Zhang et al. (2021). Other optimisation tools that come over in various articles are GUROBI and LINGO, as well as Minitab, which is also used for the design of experiments and statistical analysis (Rahman

et al. 2021). Other mentioned software includes AMPL language, Excel Evolutive Solver, Expert Choice, GAMS, jMetal, Matlab's gamultiobj, Pyomo and Simplex algorithm.

Programming languages involve the use of Python, with libraries like TensorFlow, Keras, Sklearn, DEAP, Sympy, Matplotlib, Pandas and Scikit-learn, and their related IDEs Pycharm and Spyder. Other programming languages, such as R and its libraries dplyr, C, C# and Java, also appear. Other IDEs cited in the selected bibliography include Visual Studio and CPLEX Studio.

Figure 5 Caption. Software tools identified in the selected literature.

Figure 5 Alt Text. A classification of the software tools used by the reviewed literature according to bibliography, data analytics, databases and information management, optimisation and solutions, programming languages and integrated development environments (IDEs), simulation, Web services and applications.

There is a variety of simulation software in the reviewed literature. Of the tools used by authors, AnyLogic, VENSIM and ARENA stand out for appearing in numerous

studies. However, ProModel, CATIA, Flexim, Industrial Path Solutions, Norlean Analyser Operation (NOA), SimAL, Simapro, Simio software, Technomatix Plant Simulation and UppAal SMC are also mentioned. Finally for web services and applications, Kuik and Diong (2019) use Microsoft ASP.Net for the top level of the client interface and create a virtual environment with VMware to evaluate it, while Jong et al. (2020) establish a programmable web *via* Web Form.

Furthermore information about the software used in each article can be found in Appendix III.

3.2.7 I4.0 technologies

The I4.0 technologies that appear in the selected literature are classified into 12 groups: additive manufacturing, AI, automation and robotics, blockchain, cloud computing, CPS, cybersecurity, data analytics and big data, the IoT and sensor, simulation and DT, extended reality and tracking and tracing systems (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Caption. I4.0 Technologies.

Figure 6 Alt Text. An image with icons illustrating the various grouped I4.0 technologies.

The technology group that appears most frequently is data analytics and big data for which the contribution of Kumar, Singh and Lamba (2018) is highlighted. Their study highlights the importance of big data to design efficient and effective facility layouts in today's competitive market. Data are collected based on the 3Vs (volume, variety, velocity) of big data. Nguyen et al. (2022) explore the current status, opportunities and challenges of data analytics in the pharmaceutical supply chains context. With a

systematic literature review, they conclude that although machine learning has proven to be promising in addressing problems like drug shortages and inventory management, there is still untapped potential in utilising various data resources, particularly unstructured data. Other papers use these tools to support decision systems (Salama and Eltawil 2018; Trstenjak et al. 2022), manage planned obsolescence in production (Kuik and Diong 2019), find tradeoff between rescheduling frequency and backlog accumulation through a real-time analysis (Li et al. 2020), validate mathematical models (Akkad and Bányai 2023) and update their parameters from big data sets (Tsai and Lu 2018).

AI and machine learning are also widely discussed in the literature. For example, Li et al. (2020) create machine-learning models to classify rescheduling patterns in production. Abidi, Mohammed, and Alkhalefah (2022) develop a predictive maintenance planning model with intelligent methods, including data cleaning and normalisation, feature selection, prediction network decision making and machine-learning prediction. Estes et al. (2022) focus on the use and applications of RL techniques in the PPC problems field. Zhang et al. (2022) employ deep RL to accelerate the learning process and to improve optimisation algorithm performance.

The use of the IoT and sensors is also widespread in the selected literature. Akkad and Bányai (2023) use sensors for the physical level of the control of their model and an IoT gateway through which they receive preprocessed information for monitoring. Tsai and Lu (2018) propose employing sensors and the IoT to collect and monitor the activity data of all the components of a factory in real time. Li and Wang (2022) suggest combining the IoT with cloud computing to support the solution of the green shop scheduling problem by collecting data from equipment in real time.

As already discussed, simulation strategies and technologies, together with DTs, are also widely used in the literature. Yazdi, Azizi, and Hashemipour (2019) generate a simulation model of the actual system to evaluate the performance of optimisation ideas before implementing them. The study by Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog (2023) applies simulation software to evaluate different designs of an assembly line. Groten and Gallego-García (2021) represent the steps of their conceptual model through simulation models to show improvements in the system. Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler (2021b) propose using the DT technology to simulate and optimise the MPS problem to maximise service levels, resilience and sustainability of supply chains. Bakon et al. (2022) discuss employing DTs in I4.0 by highlighting their importance in creating a

virtual equivalent of manufacturing processes and correcting uncertainties, and they also note that the importance of DTs will increase in I5.0 with the introduction of human-centred thinking.

Figure 7 Caption. Number of occurrences of each type of problem, modelling and solution approach, software tool and I4.0 technology in the selected literature.

Figure 7 Alt Text. Bar chart plot comparing the number of occurrences of each type of problem, modelling and solution approach, software tool and I4.0 technology to grasp trends.

Regarding cloud computing, Amjad, Rafique, and Khan (2021) propose a cloud-based production control system to enhance the manufacturing process by enabling real-

time visibility. Salama and Eltawil (2018) use cloud storage to upload data to provide the status of the facility through interfaces and the real-time tracking of each physical element involved in the production facility so that data are protected and accessible to decision makers and the decision support system. On CPS, Li and Huang (2021) propose a cyber-physical visibility and traceability (CPVT) system that provides real-time data through embedded data analytics so onsite operators can access local CPVT, while managers can view global CPVT, which offers historical and real-time data for dynamic analyses in production-intralogsistics synchronisation.

Finally, there are groups of technologies, such as automation and robotics, additive manufacturing, tracking and tracing systems, blockchain, extended reality (XR) and cybersecurity that appear in fewer than 10 studies in the selected literature. Appendix IV details the technologies that appear in each research work.

Figure 7 summarises the main findings related to the type of problem, modelling and solution approach, software tools and I4.0 technologies.

3.2.8 I5.0 approaches and people focus

As for the general approaches towards I5.0, concrete strategies are only detailed in eight documents as such. Bakon et al. (2022) establish the I5.0 requirements that should be addressed, such as corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainability, human-centric, worker well-being, advanced employee skills and training management, social stability, resilient against external shocks and responsive supply chain (RSC) given the tasks challenges and uncertainties to each requirement. Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog (2023) utilise the European assembly worksheet (EAWS), a screening tool that identifies ergonomic issues and provides solutions for assessing workers' posture and movements to rebalance the assembly line. Groten and Gallego-García (2021) affirm that I5.0 involves human and device cooperation in production, which brings back the human aspect to industrial production for value-added tasks and personalised products or services. Leng et al. (2022) suggest that the resilient individualised manufacturing concept to be part of the I5.0 proposition. Rega et al. (2021) affirm that collaborative robotics can replace humans in alienating tasks by creating new roles in the workplace. Lind et al. (2023) use the OWAS/Lundqvist Index to evaluate worker well-being by assessing biomechanical loads on various body parts. Zhang et al. (2021) propose that I5.0 emphasises coordinated development between humans and production factors for companies' sustainable management and development (i.e. CSR). Finally, Santos et al.

(2022) highlight that genetic algorithm use follows the key I5.0 foundations by attempting multi-objective optimisation that is human-centric, resilient and sustainable, which is the most specific optimisation approach reviewed to address I5.0, and further research into this issue is necessary. In summary, I5.0 approaches involve a blend of advanced algorithms, ergonomic assessment tools and collaborative technologies, which all focus on creating a sustainable and worker-centred production environment. These strategies illustrate a comprehensive framework for effectively meeting I5.0 goals. The focus on sustainable development promotes a balanced relation between production and human factors by empowering individuals in the workforce.

In particular, the focus on people is more relevant in the literature. Indeed 50,6% research studies mention particular people approaches. The way to introduce the approach to people in their studies is classified into five groups: descriptive (DC), decision support (DS), ergonomics (ER), employee training (ET) and human-machine collaboration (HM).

In the descriptive approach, some studies mention approaches to people as recommendations or future ideas without carrying them out. For example, Li et al. (2020) argue that the production industry's approach can be adapted to staff scheduling in hospitals to take into account daily fluctuations in emergencies, patient populations and care levels. Rega et al. (2021) propose that collaborative robotics can replace humans in alienating tasks by creating new roles in the workplace and ensuring worker safety. Finally, Goienetxea Uriarte, Ng, and Urenda Moris (2020) point out workers' reluctance to change and organisations will have to face implementing simulation strategies.

Decision making approaches also appear and take into account humans' creativity (Bakon et al. 2022; Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic 2021) and leadership (Bányai et al. 2019), while relying on data collection (Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog 2023; Dunke et al. 2018), collaboration with model-driven systems (Kuik and Diong 2019; Naderi et al. 2019; Salama and Eltawil 2018; Yu 2022) and data visualisation (Nguyen et al. 2022). In this way, more informed decisions can be made (Salama and Eltawil 2018) by prioritising different objectives (Santos et al. 2022).

Ergonomics issues take into account workers' well-being (Battini et al. 2022), discomfort (Aydin and Tirkolae 2022), safety (Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog 2023; Khettabi, Benyoucef, and Amine Boutiche 2022; Kumar, Singh, and Lamba 2018; Leong et al. 2020) and working conditions (Groten and Gallego-García 2021). Furthermore, the importance of employees' physical and mental comfort is a concept that

authors like Li, Tan, and Li (2018), Sar and Ghadimi (2022) or Tripathi et al. (2021a) highlight in their contributions.

The employee training approach is used in the literature to educate people and to improve processes (Amjad, Rafique, and Khan 2021). It resorts to factors like learning, forgetting, training in models (Aydin and Tirkolaei 2022) and organising training programmes (Tripathi et al. 2022b) to, thus, improve the work environment (Trstenjak et al. 2022). Ultimately, it is about improving employees' skills and taking these skills into account in the work they do.

Finally, human-machine collaboration through I5.0 considers workers' creativity (Bakon et al. 2022) and conditions (Groten and Gallego-García 2021) by replacing them with machines to do alienating tasks (Rega et al. 2021). Collaborative work environments are also created (Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog 2023), where security must be balanced (Rega et al. 2021) by integrating technologies like CPS, AI, machine learning and big data with employee-centric values (Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog 2023). Appendix V further analyses the focus on I5.0 and on people found in each research work.

3.2.9 *Sustainability approaches*

Finally, in sustainability approaches terms (Appendix IV), virtually all the selected articles in the literature consider one, or more, of the three pillars of sustainability, i.e. economic sustainability, environmental sustainability and social sustainability. Studies that consider only economic sustainability aim to reduce costs (Abderrahim et al. 2020; Zhang et al. 2023), optimise scheduling to cut completion times (Jong et al. 2020) and minimise the maximum production time (Li et al. 2020). The use of advanced technologies and CPS enables more efficient and sustainable production by adapting to variable demand and reducing waste (Agostino et al. 2020). Methods like reactive scheduling (Takeda-Berger et al. 2022) and deep reinforcement learning (Zhang et al. 2022) help to maintain efficiency and cost sustainability, even in the event of unexpected events. Together, these sustainability strategies aim to minimise production times and delivery costs, and to improve overall system efficiency (Pires et al. 2018; Rahman et al. 2021).

On economic and environmental sustainability, studies that focus on energy optimisation (Bányai 2021), reducing emissions (Li et al. 2022) and use (Bányai et al. 2019) stand out. Other authors employ waste reduction (Abidi, Mohammed, and

Alkhalefah 2022) and resource management (Tripathi et al. 2022a) as the means to advance towards this dual sustainability, which, as Leite, Pinto, and Alves (2019) point out, are evenly matched because sustainable thinking and environmentally-friendly decision making help companies to gain commercial advantages, while maintaining or reducing costs.

Some studies contemplate the three pillars of sustainability, and others take a holistic view of them, such as Amjad, Rafique, and Khan (2021) or Kumar, Singh, and Lamba (2018). Santos et al. (2022) focus on social issues through human-centric solutions, and also on economic and environmental pillars, by reducing costs like transport. Through SDGs, it is also possible to establish lines of action for all three pillars of sustainability (Bakon et al. 2022). Furthermore, studies like those by Naderi et al. (2019) or Li, Tan, and Li (2018) measure and set targets in models that combine all three pillars. As affirmed by Tan et al. (2023), researchers are developing algorithms to reduce not only production time, but also energy use, to achieve social, environmental and economic benefits.

In the literature, the economic and social pillars combine to meet growing individualised demands through sustainable and human-centred manufacturing (Leng et al. 2022). To achieve sustainable operations, it is crucial to balance assembly lines, manage labour costs (Li 2021) and be competitive by integrating consumer demands (Salama and Eltawil 2018).

Finally, the approach of Li and Wang (2022), applied to achieve socio-environmental sustainable development, is that society needs more efficient manufacturing methods and technologies that save energy and to reduce emissions. Furthermore, Demartini et al. (2021) state that sustainability aspects are missing and suggest specific developments in this direction.

4. Discussion

This article reviews the literature on optimisation problems for managing production or operations by a sustainable approach in I4.0 or I5.0. The answers to the formulated RQs are discussed below.

As regards the main characteristics of optimisation models and algorithms for production or operations management, and their solutions, which aim to move towards

more sustainable I4.0/I5.0 (RQ1), Figure 8 presents an overview of the key findings from the categorisation of the reviewed articles.

The studies selected from the literature address various sectors and economic activities as application contexts, such as manufacturing, machinery, automotive, food, rubber and plastic, pharmaceutical products, construction, transportation and storage and waste collection. This study also points out that almost half the research is applied in undefined manufacturing contexts or through data generation. So their application in specific contexts can be challenging, which may limit their practical utility. In this way, however, they are not limited to a specific context. In terms of application contexts, studies focus on a specific company or several stakeholders in the supply chain. The objectives sought in the literature are divided into development and validation of models, proposal and implementation of management strategies, performance evaluation of models, review and analysis of the literature and implementation of I4.0 tools. So as we can see, they cover a wide range of approaches and applications in the studied field.

The studied problems are divided according to their decision level, i.e., strategical, tactical and operational, the SCOR process, i.e., source, make and delivery, and the type of problem. Additionally, the research methodology is provided: conceptual, descriptive, empirical, exploratory cross-sectional or exploratory longitudinal. Modelling and solving approaches are presented in different ways to achieve their objectives and solutions: conceptual framework, heuristic, LM techniques, machine learning, manufacturing strategies, mathematical programming, metaheuristic, simulation, statistical analysis and others. We note that several papers (Table 5) study more than one problem and interrelate them, especially in supply chain contexts. In addition, various software tools are considered to present and solve these problems. They are classified into bibliographic tools, data analysis tools, database and information management tools, optimisation and solution tools, programming languages and IDEs, simulation environments, and web services or applications.

Figure 8 Caption. Categorisation of selected articles.

Figure 8 Alt Text. Graph summarising the main conclusions of the categorisation of the reviewed articles.

Finally, different approaches are taken into account in the different studies, towards I4.0 or I5.0 technologies, towards people, and also towards sustainability. Approaches towards I4.0 are sometimes the main focus of studies, as seen in Bányai (2021) or Salama and Eltawil (2018). Other approaches are oriented towards sustainability, I5.0 and people by focusing on integrating more responsible practices through indicators, constraints, among others. In addition, some studies focus on people and somehow seek to improve the interaction and impact of new technologies and strategies on the workforce and society at large. We also note that I4.0 and 5.0 integration can indeed lead to improvements in sustainability and responsible practices (Felsberger and Reiner 2020). These technologies can promote more responsible practices by incorporating indicators and restrictions to benefit economical, environmental and social sustainability. This holistic approach ensures that technological progresses align with sustainable and ethical goals. With this classification, practitioners, academics and researchers can easily access the studied problems and approaches and orient them to the concrete application in their company or supply chain.

As for the main research gaps, challenges and trends for further research in the optimisation of production or operations management problems to move towards more sustainable I4.0/I5.0 (RQ2), the main challenges identified in the literature lie in production scheduling problems. These challenges focus on: integrating more variables into models that take in mind, for example, machine maintenance costs (Abderrahim et al. 2020); contemplating both the structure of processes and their specific functions (Ivanov et al. 2018); implementing decision support systems in real CPS (Salama and Eltawil 2018); improving system adaptability and decision making in I4.0 environments, integrating with lean, smart, green and other optimisation techniques to improve operational and environmental performance on the shop floor (Tripathi et al. 2021a; 2021b; 2022a; 2022b). Examples of challenges in other types of problems include balancing diversification and intensification in heuristic algorithms (Awad and Abd-Elaziz 2021), improving the industrial data analysis (Aydin and Tirkolaei 2022), integrating risk models into advanced planning systems (Dunke et al. 2018), and adapting robust models to big data and machine learning for I5.0 (Leong et al. 2020).

Limitations at the strategical decision level include the fact that certain steps of algorithms are still solved by hand, lack of integration of genetic algorithms and ergonomic issues (Breznik, Buchmeister, and Vujica Herzog 2023), the exclusion of key studies due to the required terminology (i.e., perishable supply chains) (Mirabelli and

Solina 2022) and the constant updating of databases in literature reviews (Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler 2021a; Zhou et al. 2022). Unstructured data are also underutilised due to their inconsistency and incompleteness, scalability, timeliness and security (Nguyen et al. 2022). Moreover, energy issues like efficiency, planning, performance, demand, or savings, among others, are not included in algorithms (Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic 2021). Some models ignore the economic considerations of resources and decision support systems are based on final human confirmation (Serrano-Ruiz, Mula, and Poler 2021b). At the tactical decision level of problems, limitations include limited focus on quality, remanufacturing and environmental issues (Demartini et al. 2021), omission in decision support systems of variations in component life cycles due to wear and tear and technological cycles (Kuik and Diong 2019), and lack of generalisation and comparison between flexible or reconfigurable and rigid or static reverse logistics systems (Yu 2022). Limitations at the operational decision level include the use of deterministic supply demands rather than stochastic parameters that do not consider the expensive investment and operational costs in I4.0 technologies (Akkad and Bányai 2023), and the difficulty in making decisions with multiple objectives because it can become overwhelming due to the large number of objectives and, consequently, solutions, and also because multi-objective optimisation tools are lacking (Santos et al. 2022). In addition, disruptions like machine breakdowns or cancellation of orders, and industry variations like company size and segment, are not included (Takeda-Berger et al. 2022).

We divide trends for future studies into four main groups. The first of the groups is about optimisation technologies and models. In it, we highlight several advanced approaches, such as the incorporation of deterministic and stochastic models with fuzzy logic to analyse the in-plant supply (Akkad and Bányai 2023), genetic algorithms and metaheuristics to reduce computational times for large instances in NP-hard problems (Battini et al. 2022). The following ideas are also included in this first group: AI techniques for dynamic control to achieve consistent manufacturing control in constantly changing scenarios (Leng et al. 2022); blockchain-based smart contracts for sharing resources securely and transparently (Ramakurthi et al. 2022); algorithms for multi-objective decision making about industrial buildings production planning (Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic 2021), energy use (Rahman et al. 2021) and aspects like worker well-being, productivity, production sequencing with product variants, moving assembly lines, staff safety and regulations (Lind et al. 2023). Other research work for the future includes the optimisation of ecological scheduling problems and the use of dynamic

simulations with multiple agents (Zhang et al. 2022). The second group is about the integration of I4.0 and I5.0, ideas for future studies include the integration of sustainable VSM and ergonomics with I4.0 techniques, such as big data or the IoT to optimise supply chain performance (Amjad, Rafique, and Khan 2021), and developing models that consider the unpredictable nature of human behaviour in I5.0 (Bakon et al. 2022). The assessment of industry readiness for I4.0 integration in global supply chains (Farooq et al. 2021), the validation of sustainable models to bridge the gap between strategy and implementation (Mula and Bogataj 2021), and the implementation of methodologies to help digitisation in small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Naderi et al. 2019), are also highlighted. Other ideas include enhancing decision making in complex distributed networks (Agostino et al. 2020) for stochastics and dynamic behaviours (Pires, Parreira, and Frazzon 2021), and logistics synchronisation in smart manufacturing systems in flow shop or job shop scenarios (Li and Huang 2021). The third group aims to improve supply chains by studying multiproduct supply networks. We also find the impact of leadership style on organisational performance (Bányai 2021), the formulation of energy-aware scheduling problems (Para, Del Ser, and Nebro 2022) and machine-learning use to optimise inventories (Nguyen et al. 2022). Other approaches address the design of reverse logistics networks with vehicle routing to optimise travel distances among customers, collection centres and manufacturers to allow dynamic routing plans (Sar and Ghadimi 2022), and the impact of the IoT and the closed-loop supply chain design on sustainability and CSR (Zhang et al. 2021). Finally, the fourth group consists of ideas for future research into the development and evaluation of algorithms and heuristics. Ideas include using metaheuristics for design cellular layouts with uneven areas (Kumar, Singh, and Lamba 2018), allocating workers to workstations by employing skill matrices (Li 2021) and improving dynamic VSM efficiency with large datasets (Ramadan et al. 2020). There are also suggestions to include energy planners and flexibility metrics for design purposes in multi-objective optimisation (Reisinger, Hollinsky, and Kovacic 2021) and to adapt approaches to diverse industries, of different sizes and sectors, and disruptions, like machine failures (Takeda-Berger et al. 2022). Finally, works on systematic reviews (Tan et al. 2023), lean analyses as a support for decision making (Goienetxea Uriarte, Ng, and Urenda Moris 2020) and the extension of methodologies for long-term evaluations of case studies (Yazdi, Azizi, and Hashemipour 2019), are encouraged.

Figure 9 presents an overview of the main challenges, limitations and trends for future studies, which are identified in the previous paragraphs, classified by the categories

of the review. Appendix VI contains any identified limitations, challenges or suggested areas for further research in each study.

	Main challenges	Limitations	Trends for future studies
Application context		OP Disruptions and industry variations were not included	Implementation of methodologies in small- and medium-sized enterprises Adapt approaches to diverse industries and disruptions Study multiproduct supply networks Enhance decision making in complex distributed networks
Research methodology		ST Exclusion of studies due to terminology ST Ongoing update of databases in literature reviews	Dedication to systematic reviews
Modelling and solution approach	Integrating variables into models to consider costs	ST Certain steps of algorithms are still solved by hand	Use of dynamic simulations with multiple agents
	Integrating risk models into advanced planning systems	ST Lack of integration of genetic algorithms	Improving dynamic value stream mapping efficiency with large datasets
	Balancing diversification and intensification in heuristic algorithms	ST Unstructured data are underutilised	Extension of methodologies for long-term evaluations
	Current models omit financial considerations	TA Omission of variations in the life span of components wear-out and technology cycles in decision support systems models	Incorporation of deterministic and stochastic models with fuzzy logic
	OP Use of deterministic rather than stochastic parameters	Genetic algorithms and metaheuristics to reduce computational times	
	OP Difficulty in making decisions with multiple objectives	Algorithms for multi-objective decision-making	
		OP Lean analysis for decision-making	
Problem	Considering both the structure of the processes and their specific functions.	TA Limited focus on remanufacturing	Formulation of energy scheduling problems
		TA Lack of comparison between flexible and rigid reverse logistics systems	Design of reverse logistics networks
I4.0	Implementing decision support systems in real CPS		Assessment of industry readiness for I4.0 and AI integration
	Improving industrial data analysis	OP Lack of consideration of costs in I4.0 technologies	Logistics synchronisation in smart manufacturing systems
	Improving system adaptability and decision making in I4.0 environments		Blockchain-based smart contracts AI use for dynamic control
I5.0	Adapting robust models to big data and machine learning for I5.0		Focus on human behaviour in I5.0 Impact of the IoT and the closed-loop supply chain design on sustainability and CSR
Focus on people		ST Lack of integration of ergonomics issues	Allocating workers using skill matrices
		ST Decision support systems rely on human confirmation	Impact of leadership style on organisational performance
Sustainability	Integrating lean, smart, green and other optimisation techniques to improve operational and environmental performance on the shop floor		Include energy planners and flexibility metrics for multi-objective optimisation
	Energy issues are not included in the algorithms		Validation of sustainable models
			Optimisation of ecological scheduling problems Integration of sustainable value stream mapping and ergonomics with I4.0 techniques

Note: Strategical (ST); tactical (TA); operational (OP)

Figure 9 Caption. Main identified challenges, limitations and trends for future studies.

Figure 9 Alt Text. Graph summarising the main identified challenges, limitations and trends for future studies from the reviewed articles.

5. Conclusions

The theoretical implications of this work focus on proposing an analytical classification (Figure 8) that structures and organises knowledge of optimising PPC problems (Table 5) in a sustainable and I4.0 or I5.0 context to, thus, facilitate the interrelation between categories, their understanding and future consultation. This classification can also serve as a basis for future research (Figure 9). The systematic literature review was conducted by taking a holistic approach that, through the CIMO model, facilitated the matching of keywords to identify PPC optimisation problems to move towards more sustainable I4.0 and I5.0. This provides a clear framework that identifies and categorises current challenges, and highlights emerging trends in this research and practitioner field.

The main findings identify that the main setting of PPC optimisation problems lies in manufacturing contexts and highlight the use of modelling and solution techniques through mathematical programming and metaheuristics (Table 6). The included studies, mostly empirical, point out the use of different software tools by underlining MATLAB, CPLEX, Python libraries and AnyLogic. For I4.0 techniques, data analytics and big data, AI, the IoT and sensors and simulation and DTs are the most widely studied (Figure 7). The proposals addressing worker ergonomics and a three-pillar approach to sustainability are particularly noteworthy.

The managerial implications of this study centre on providing an analytical classification that structures knowledge about optimisation issues in production and operations management in the sustainability and Industry 4.0/5.0 context. This categorisation makes it easier for managers to more effectively identify and address the specific challenges they face in their operations. Providing a clear framework facilitates the adoption of sustainable practices, I4.0 or I5.0 technologies, and people-focused approaches to, therefore, improve business performance and societal resilience. In addition, the systematic literature review enables managers to understand current trends and practices that have already been carried out in previous studies and their results. This can guide decision making because leaders can apply knowledge from these previous studies to develop and implement models that optimise their processes. Finally, this research highlights the importance of fostering a business culture that values sustainability, adopts I4.0 technologies and focuses on people, which can all lead to a competitive advantage in increasingly demanding markets.

This systematic literature review faces several limitations. Firstly, despite a systematic search process, some valuable articles may have been overlooked for this review because of the formulated search queries. Conversely, the choice of keywords, which intended to limit studies to those that met a number of requirements turned out, for instance with sustainability, to be a very strict requirement for searching titles, abstracts and keywords, and extending it to the whole document could have been misleading because the word might appear in, for example, references. Moreover, although the main focus of this article lies on PPC based on the used keywords, the scheduling and supply chain concepts are also present in the reviewed articles (Figure 7). However, the lot sizing term is notably absent. Hence the distinction between production planning and lot sizing can be subtle (Suzanne, Absi, and Borodin 2020). Thus the omission of lot sizing from the selected keywords could lead to a misleading of a substantial body of literature. Secondly, the review took into account five databases (Scopus, WoS, ScienceDirect, ProQuest and IEEE Xplore) that, although diverse, could have missed valuable studies in this field and, besides, the provided data are constantly updated and correspond to the time when the research was carried out. Lastly, new databases like arXiv could be taken into account in future research.

In view of the results of this review, future directions for research are oriented to: (i) study the implementation of methodologies in SMEs, such as digitisation and the change towards I4.0/I5.0; (ii) address optimisation problems approaches to diverse industries, of different sizes and sectors, disruptions, such as machine failures or stocks outs, and multiproduct scenarios; (iii) improve decision making in distributed networks with multi-objective algorithms and lean analysis to facilitate human final choices; (iv) incorporate dynamic simulations with multiple agents to represent complex environments; (v) incorporate large datasets, long-term evaluations of problems and deterministic with stochastic models and fuzzy logic using genetic algorithms and metaheuristic to reduce computational time in complex problems; (vi) developing energy and ecological programming and designing reverse logistics networks, in short more sustainability-conscious problems; (vii) assess industrial readiness for I4.0 by taking into account implementation and operational costs; (viii) evaluate the impact of leadership style on organisational performance, the influence of I4.0 technologies on sustainability and CSR, and include the focus on human behaviour by considering employees' skills for work; (ix) validate sustainable models, include energy planners in optimisation models

and integrate sustainability and ergonomics with I4.0 techniques to achieve sustainability compromised manufacturing.

Finally, forthcoming works focus on proposing a new conceptual framework to define and categorise the concepts and variables related to sustainability, ergonomics and human behaviour in PPC problems. Thus the aim is to use this conceptual framework as a basis for new quantitative models that consider sustainability, people-centred approaches and I4.0 tools to move towards more efficient and people-centred I5.0.

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Data availability statement

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available in the article and in Appendices included as supplementary files.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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